

Temperature dependence of density, conductance and viscosity of zinc sulphate and copper sulphate solutions in aqueous medium in the presence of maltose and sodium chloride

Shashi Kant Lomesh* and Dinesh Kumar

Department of Chemistry, Himachal Pradesh University, Summer Hill, Shimla-171 005,
Himachal Pradesh, India

E-mail : dinesh744227@gmail.com

Manuscript received online 17 November 2016, accepted 09 December 2016

Abstract : Density (ρ), viscosity (η) and molar conductance (Λ_m) for hepta-hydrated zinc sulphate ($\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and penta-hydrated copper sulphate ($\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$) have been measured in aqueous systems modified with maltose and sodium chloride at different temperatures (298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K). The above measured parameters were then employed to obtain apparent molar volume (ϕ_v), relative viscosity (η_{rel}) and molar conductance (Λ_m). The apparent molar volume was fitted in Masson's equation, relative viscosity in Jones-Dole equation and molar conductance into Onsager's equation to obtain secondary thermodynamic functions including limiting apparent molar volume (ϕ_v^0), A and B coefficients of Jones-Dole equation and limiting molar conductance (Λ_m^0). The effects of concentration and temperature on these parameters were studied and discussed in terms of ion-solvent and ion-ion interactions. The variation of ion-solvent and ion-ion interactions and Walden product ($\Lambda_m^0 \eta_0$) suggested structure-making nature of these electrolytes in aqueous systems modified with maltose and sodium chloride.

Keywords : Density, viscosity, molar conductance, maltose, sodium chloride.

Introduction

Behaviour of a liquid can be described easily by knowing intra-solute, intra-solvent and solute-solvent interactions. Considering the aqueous-ionic solutions, the interactions among the ions i.e. the interactions between ion-solvent and ion-ion can determine interactions in solutions which are useful to understand the behaviour of solute in that solvent or vice versa. The interactions in liquid systems can be estimated by parameters related to molar volume, viscosity and conductance. Limiting apparent molar volumes of electrolytes, B parameter of Jones-Dole equation and molar conductance at infinite dilution can be employed to explain various types of interactions in the solutions. The nature of these interactions is further useful to explain structural changes occurring in the solutions.

Studies on the interactions of ions with saccharides can provide important information about physiological systems and can be used in the separation and purification processes for biomaterials. Therefore, a great deal

of interest has developed in the studies of electrolytes in aqueous saccharide solutions. The toxicity of metals in environment is of increased concern that has led to increase research activity to identify the fate of these metal ions in the organisms.

Maltose is used as an immediate source of energy along with glucose. It is a disaccharide and water soluble sugar. Maltose is used in a number of biological processes as a stabilising agent or osmolality regulator. Therefore it is very important to study the behaviour of electrolytes in aqueous maltose solutions. The structure of alpha-D-maltose is shown below :

The study of interactions and behaviour of electrolytes and metal ions in aqueous carbohydrate solutions is

very important and also a major area for research. Since small amount of metal ions are present in biological fluid i.e. intracellular or extracellular bio fluids so the study of these ions in aqueous solutions of carbohydrates is quite important and exciting. The molecular interactions of sugars in aqueous solutions of metal ions play important role in governing the biological and medicinal mechanism of any system⁹. Zinc is essential to maintain normal vitamin-A level in blood plasma and regulation of insulin function. It is also used in tissue repair and wound healing. The normal requirement of Zn is 15 mg/day and is provided by milk, sea food, meat and food grains. Copper is essential to life to life and an adult human contains about 100 mg. About 4–5 g of copper is required in daily diet. The copper is bound to proteins in body either as metallo-proteins or as enzymes. It act as anti inflammatory and anti infectious and take part in cell generation^{1–12}.

In present work we have studied metal sulphates i.e. $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ternary system containing 0.02, 0.04 and 0.06 mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 mol kg^{-1} aqueous NaCl solutions at temperatures 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K in order to understand the nature of solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions by measuring the density, molar volume, molar conductance and viscosity of their solutions.

Experimental

Chemicals used : Zinc sulphate, copper sulphate, sodium chloride and maltose used for this study were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich. All chemicals were of analytical grade and other information quoted by the supplier is also given in Table 1. The chemicals were not purified further but were kept in vacuum oven to remove any moisture if present. Distilled water obtained from series

of distillations has been employed as primary solvent. Water purity has been determined by density measurement.

Preparation of solutions : Mass measurement method was employed to prepare solutions using an analytical balance. A solution of 0.01 mol kg^{-1} of sodium chloride in water was used as primary solvent. All the studies were made in three solvents prepared by taking 0.02, 0.04 and 0.06 mass fraction of maltose in primary solvent. Seven concentrations of zinc sulphate and copper sulphate were prepared ranging from 0.01 mol kg^{-1} to 0.12 mol kg^{-1} in all three solvents.

Instrumentation : Mass measurement were made using an analytical balance supplied by Dhona Instruments Pvt. Ltd. with precision 1×10^{-5} g. Various densities were recorded by DSA (Density and Sound Analyzer) 5000 supplied by Anton Paar, GmbH, Garz, Austria. Viscosity was determined with the help of capillary type Viscometer¹³. The conductance was measured with the help of calibrated digital conductivity meter, Elico Limited. The uncertainty in density measurements was $\pm 3.2 \times 10^{-5}$ g cm^{-3} . These studies were carried out at atmospheric pressure $p = 0.1$ MPa and four different temperatures $T = (298.15, 303.15, 308.15 \text{ and } 313.15)$ K with an accuracy of ± 0.05 K.

Results and discussion

Molar volume studies :

The apparent molar volume of zinc sulphate (or copper sulphate) in various solvents at particular temperature was calculated using densities of solution (ρ) and density of solvent (ρ^0) using expression

$$\phi_v = (M_2/\rho) - 1000(\rho - \rho^0)/m\rho\rho^0 \quad (1)$$

where M_2 represents the molecular weight of zinc sulphate (or copper sulphate). The errors in apparent molar volume were estimated by expression

$$\Delta\phi_v = (2\Delta\rho/\rho^2)(1000/m + M_2) \quad (2)$$

and were ranging from $\pm 0.06 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ to $\pm 0.10 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ for all concentrations of zinc sulphate (or copper sulphate) in various solvents.

ϕ_v varies linearly with \sqrt{m} (Figs. 1 and 2) and linear fitting was used to obtain intercept (ϕ_v^0) and slope (S_v). Limiting apparent molar volume (ϕ_v^0) of zinc sulphate (or

Table 1. Physical properties of the solvents and salts used

Solvent	ρ (g cm^{-3}) (298.15 K)	Literature value ⁶ (298.15 K)
Water	0.99712	0.99714
(as reported by the supplier)		
Salt	Melting point, T_m (K)	Mass fraction purity
Copper sulphate	383	≥ 0.99
Zinc sulphate	373	≥ 0.99
Sodium chloride	1074	≥ 0.99
Maltose	393	≥ 0.99

Fig. 1. Apparent molar volume ϕ_v as a function of square root of molal concentration \sqrt{m} for copper sulphate in 0.02 mass fraction of maltose + 0.01 mol kg⁻¹ aqueous sodium chloride at different temperatures.

Fig. 2. Apparent molar volume ϕ_v as a function of square root of molal concentration \sqrt{m} for zinc sulphate in 0.02 mass fraction of maltose + 0.01 mol kg⁻¹ aqueous sodium chloride at different temperatures.

copper sulphate) was obtained as intercept of Masson's eq. (3),

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^0 + S_v \sqrt{m} \quad (3)$$

here S_v is the experimental slope and m is the molality of the solution.

The values of apparent limiting molar volume and slopes S_v are recorded in Table 2. The slope S_v in Masson's

equation may be attributed to be as a measure of ion-ion or solute-solute interactions¹⁴⁻¹⁶. The low, positive and decreasing values of S_v account for the decrease in inter ionic interactions with increase in temperature for zinc sulphate and copper sulphate in 0.02, 0.04 and 0.06 mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 mol kg⁻¹ aqueous NaCl solutions.

The ϕ_v^0 is a measure of solute-solvent interactions¹⁷. The ϕ_v^0 values for zinc sulphate and copper sulphate increased with temperature in all solvents (Figs. 3 and 4) suggesting the increase in ion solvent interactions. The

Fig. 3. Limiting apparent molar volume ϕ_v^0 as a function of temperature T for copper sulphate in different mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 mol kg⁻¹ aqueous sodium chloride.

Fig. 4. Limiting apparent molar volume ϕ_v^0 as a function of temperature T for zinc sulphate in different mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 mol kg⁻¹ aqueous sodium chloride.

Table 2. Experimental density ρ , apparent molar volume ϕ_v , relative viscosity η_s/η_0 and molar conductance Λ_m at molality m for the system maltose (1) + water (2) + NaCl (3) + CuSO₄ (4) (or ZnSO₄ (4)) at temperatures $T = (298.15, 303.15, 308.15 \text{ and } 313.15) \text{ K}$ and pressure $p = 0.1 \text{ MPa}^a$

$m \text{ (mol kg}^{-1}\text{)}$	$\rho \text{ (g cm}^{-3}\text{)}$		$\phi_v \text{ (cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}\text{)}$		η_s/η_0		$\Lambda_m \text{ (}\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}\text{)}$	
	CuSO ₄	ZnSO ₄	CuSO ₄	ZnSO ₄	CuSO ₄	ZnSO ₄	CuSO ₄	ZnSO ₄
$T \text{ (K)} = 298.15$								
0.02 mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride								
$\rho^0 \text{ (g cm}^{-3}\text{)} = 1.00488, \eta_0 = 0.9094$								
0.01	1.00658	1.00654	80.68	122.86	1.0062	1.0045	169.06	184.69
0.02	1.00823	1.00817	82.42	123.40	1.0104	1.0080	154.70	169.44
0.04	1.01147	1.01142	84.81	123.94	1.0177	1.0144	130.76	148.23
0.06	1.01463	1.01463	86.74	124.50	1.0243	1.0207	114.82	132.20
0.08	1.01775	1.01781	88.12	124.83	1.0307	1.0269	98.42	121.02
0.10	1.02080	1.02096	89.42	125.26	1.0370	1.0329	85.70	109.96
0.12	1.02380	1.02410	90.64	125.45	1.0429	1.0389	74.00	102.89
0.04 mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride								
$\rho^0 \text{ (g cm}^{-3}\text{)} = 1.01236, \eta_0 = 0.9314$								
0.01	1.01402	1.01400	84.73	124.13	1.0040	1.0042	185.08	205.78
0.02	1.01564	1.01562	86.44	125.10	1.0073	1.0079	167.97	186.59
0.04	1.01884	1.01880	88.06	126.48	1.0140	1.0143	143.03	152.89
0.06	1.02196	1.02193	89.63	127.53	1.0201	1.0204	122.03	129.07
0.08	1.02503	1.02501	90.91	128.37	1.0263	1.0263	106.41	109.16
0.10	1.02807	1.02807	91.95	128.98	1.0323	1.0321	93.03	90.75
0.12	1.03105	1.03109	92.97	129.57	1.0381	1.0379	80.82	76.23
0.06 mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride								
$\rho^0 \text{ (g cm}^{-3}\text{)} = 1.01961, \eta_0 = 0.9661$								
0.01	1.02118	1.02125	94.01	124.85	1.0031	1.0051	199.97	220.10
0.02	1.02272	1.02288	95.41	125.18	1.0060	1.0089	178.72	195.40
0.04	1.02573	1.02609	97.28	125.80	1.0113	1.0159	148.04	160.20
0.06	1.02868	1.02928	98.60	126.14	1.0163	1.0222	126.01	138.10
0.08	1.03159	1.03244	99.77	126.48	1.0216	1.0287	106.09	115.20
0.10	1.03443	1.03557	100.90	126.80	1.0268	1.0349	92.07	96.36
0.12	1.03724	1.03868	101.90	127.06	1.0320	1.0408	77.85	82.12
$T \text{ (K)} = 303.15$								
0.02 mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride								
$\rho^0 \text{ (g cm}^{-3}\text{)} = 1.00343, \eta_0 = 0.8146$								
0.01	1.00511	1.00509	81.35	123.50	1.0069	1.0050	195.43	215.83
0.02	1.00676	1.00671	82.94	123.94	1.0112	1.0084	177.20	197.79
0.04	1.00999	1.00994	85.24	124.56	1.0190	1.0150	146.71	173.44
0.06	1.01314	1.01314	87.23	125.03	1.0258	1.0214	127.62	153.40
0.08	1.01623	1.01631	88.73	125.40	1.0323	1.0275	110.74	138.41
0.10	1.01928	1.01945	90.02	125.78	1.0386	1.0337	97.54	124.81
0.12	1.02230	1.02257	90.97	126.08	1.0446	1.0398	85.91	112.85
0.04 mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride								
$\rho^0 \text{ (g cm}^{-3}\text{)} = 1.01086, \eta_0 = 0.8350$								
0.01	1.01251	1.00509	86.18	123.50	1.0047	1.0050	212.25	215.83
0.02	1.01412	1.00671	87.60	123.94	1.0082	1.0084	192.93	197.79

Table-2 (contd.)

0.04	1.01728	1.00994	89.44	124.56	1.0150	1.0150	163.72	173.44
0.06	1.02038	1.01314	90.94	125.03	1.0218	1.0214	141.51	153.40
0.08	1.02343	1.01631	92.19	125.40	1.0278	1.0275	124.47	138.41
0.10	1.02642	1.01945	93.36	125.78	1.0337	1.0337	110.42	124.81
0.12	1.02939	1.02257	94.23	126.08	1.0401	1.0398	96.65	112.85
0.06 mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride								
ρ^0 (g cm ⁻³) = 1.01809, η_0 = 0.857/8								
0.01	1.01963	1.01972	96.05	125.38	1.0042	1.0055	228.88	257.30
0.02	1.02114	1.02134	97.69	125.71	1.0073	1.0093	205.25	229.70
0.04	1.02411	1.02454	99.47	126.23	1.0130	1.0164	169.80	192.50
0.06	1.02702	1.02772	100.80	126.69	1.0184	1.0228	143.79	163.60
0.08	1.02988	1.03087	101.90	126.99	1.0240	1.0291	123.68	138.70
0.10	1.03268	1.03399	103.00	127.31	1.0294	1.0355	105.90	115.80
0.12	1.03596	1.03709	103.80	127.55	1.0347	1.0414	90.05	99.18
T (K) = 308.15								
0.02 mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride								
ρ^0 (g cm ⁻³) = 1.00177, η_0 = 0.73389								
0.01	1.00344	1.00342	82.30	124.23	1.0079	1.0054	220.95	247.22
0.02	1.00508	1.00504	84.00	124.68	1.0125	1.0090	194.95	227.14
0.04	1.00829	1.00826	86.16	125.34	1.0204	1.0154	168.82	199.49
0.06	1.01143	1.01145	88.05	125.63	1.0274	1.0219	140.17	173.17
0.08	1.01450	1.01460	89.52	126.05	1.0343	1.0282	123.73	154.53
0.10	1.01755	1.01772	90.62	126.51	1.0412	1.0344	109.53	135.51
0.12	1.02052	1.02083	91.83	126.76	1.0474	1.0406	98.06	122.80
0.04 mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride								
ρ^0 (g cm ⁻³) = 1.00918, η_0 = 0.7528								
0.01	1.01080	1.01080	88.41	126.57	1.0056	1.0052	241.57	291.22
0.02	1.01238	1.01239	89.74	127.34	1.0094	1.0087	221.47	257.15
0.04	1.01551	1.01553	91.41	128.61	1.0165	1.0152	190.53	213.79
0.06	1.01858	1.01862	92.77	129.53	1.0233	1.0214	164.32	179.86
0.08	1.02158	1.02166	94.01	130.37	1.0297	1.0274	142.85	147.03
0.10	1.02455	1.02468	95.08	131.02	1.0362	1.0335	125.18	120.18
0.12	1.02745	1.02765	96.16	131.66	1.0423	1.0395	110.20	100.74
0.06 mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride								
ρ^0 (g cm ⁻³) = 1.01635, η_0 = 0.7739								
0.01	1.01788	1.01797	98.18	126.59	1.0051	1.0059	256.03	298.70
0.02	1.01938	1.01958	99.15	126.92	1.0085	1.0098	229.51	268.70
0.04	1.02232	1.02276	100.80	127.41	1.0148	1.0172	191.66	221.60
0.06	1.02520	1.02591	102.10	127.83	1.0204	1.0237	161.65	185.40
0.08	1.02802	1.02903	103.30	128.20	1.0262	1.0301	138.34	156.60
0.10	1.03080	1.03213	104.40	128.46	1.0317	1.0364	117.76	133.40
0.12	1.03355	1.03520	105.20	128.75	1.0374	1.0424	99.88	112.50
T (K) = 313.15								
0.02 mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride								
ρ^0 (g cm ⁻³) = 0.99991, η_0 = 0.6644								
0.01	1.00158	1.00156	83.24	124.86	1.0087	1.0060	247.58	288.47

Table-2 (contd.)

0.02	1.00321	1.00318	84.85	125.31	1.0136	1.0098	221.07	261.65
0.04	1.00640	1.00638	86.97	125.90	1.0221	1.0163	189.82	225.94
0.06	1.00951	1.00955	88.83	126.33	1.0293	1.0229	164.98	198.58
0.08	1.01259	1.01269	90.13	126.72	1.0365	1.0295	144.73	174.79
0.10	1.01555	1.01581	91.45	126.99	1.0431	1.0357	124.33	154.23
0.12	1.01856	1.01890	92.62	127.28	1.0493	1.0422	108.71	137.88
0.04 mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride								
ρ^0 (g cm ⁻³) = 1.00730, η_0 = 0.6735								
0.01	1.00890	1.00891	90.05	127.88	1.0068	1.0056	273.63	334.19
0.02	1.01048	1.01048	91.19	128.67	1.0109	1.0093	250.83	296.88
0.04	1.01357	1.01360	92.96	129.84	1.0184	1.0161	215.06	243.93
0.06	1.01660	1.01667	94.35	130.65	1.0255	1.0221	188.85	198.64
0.08	1.01958	1.01970	95.51	131.36	1.0326	1.0284	166.18	164.10
0.10	1.02252	1.02270	96.48	131.94	1.0390	1.0344	145.85	135.63
0.12	1.02541	1.02567	97.44	132.45	1.0457	1.0403	128.28	113.49
0.06 mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride								
ρ^0 (g cm ⁻³) = 1.014444, η_0 = 0.6956								
0.01	1.01594	1.01604	100.52	128.18	1.0063	1.0064	288.10	347.20
0.02	1.01742	1.01763	101.15	128.52	1.0102	1.0103	258.70	309.20
0.04	1.02033	1.02078	102.50	129.04	1.0171	1.0177	218.43	254.50
0.06	1.02319	1.02389	103.58	129.43	1.0233	1.0242	186.02	213.50
0.08	1.02601	1.02699	104.43	129.73	1.0295	1.0307	157.90	183.50
0.10	1.02875	1.03005	105.63	130.01	1.0350	1.0371	134.81	154.90
0.12	1.03149	1.03309	106.26	130.27	1.0408	1.0434	113.80	129.40

^am is the molality of CuSO₄ or ZnSO₄ in 0.01 mol kg⁻¹ (maltose + water + NaCl) solvent. Standard uncertainties *U* are *U* (*T*) = 0.05 K, *U* (ρ) = 0.000032 g cm⁻³.

more free solvent molecules which may solvate metal ions to more extent increase with rise in temperature and hence interactions among solute-solvent increases.

The temperature dependence of ϕ_v for ZnSO₄ and CuSO₄ can be expressed by the following relations :

$$\phi_v^0 = a_0 + a_1T + a_2T^2 \quad (4)$$

Separate relations were formed for each electrolyte in different solvents and were solved for the values of a_0 , a_1 and a_2 by the method of elimination. Thus obtained values are represented in the Table 3.

The limiting apparent molar expansibility defined as $\phi_E^0 = [\partial\phi_v^0/\partial T]_p$ was also calculated using eq. (5) and is reported in Table 4.

$$\phi_E^0 = a_1 + 2a_2T \quad (5)$$

ϕ_E^0 increases with increase in temperature for zinc sulphate (or copper sulphate) in all the solvents indicating (Figs. 5 and 6) thereby the presence of caging effect in

Table 3. Values of various coefficients (a_0 , a_1 and a_2) of eq. (4) for the system maltose (1) + water (2) + NaCl (3) + CuSO₄ (4) (or ZnSO₄ (4)) at temperatures *T* = (298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15) K and pressure *p* = 0.1 MPa^a

Electrolyte	a_0 (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	a_1 (cm ³ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	a_2 (cm ³ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻²)
0.02 mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride			
CuSO ₄	310.45	-1.683	0.0030
ZnSO ₄	1443.08	-4.670	0.0008
0.04 mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride			
CuSO ₄	314.09	-1.885	0.0035
ZnSO ₄	578.28	-3.280	0.0059
0.06 mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride			
CuSO ₄	413.11	-2.586	0.0050
ZnSO ₄	1113.94	-6.690	0.0113

the system¹⁸. Water molecules interact strongly with ions which are electrically charged atoms or molecules. Dissolution of ordinary salts like NaCl in water yields a solution containing the ions Na⁺ and Cl⁻. Owing to its

Table 4. Limiting apparent molar volume ϕ_v^0 , experimental slopes S_V and apparent molar volume expansibility ϕ_E^0 , Falkenhagen coefficient A , Jones-Dole coefficient B , limiting molar conductance Λ_m^0 and Walden's $\eta_0\Lambda_m^0$ product for the system maltose (1) + water (2) + NaCl (3) + CuSO₄ (4) (or ZnSO₄ (4)) at temperatures $T = (298.15, 303.15, 308.15 \text{ and } 313.15) \text{ K}$ and pressure $p = 0.1 \text{ MPa}^d$

$T \text{ (K)}$	$\phi_v^0 = \bar{V}_2^0$ ($\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)		S_V ($\text{cm}^3 \text{ L}^{1/2} \text{ mol}^{-3/2}$)		ϕ_E^0 ($\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$)		A ($\text{dm}^3/2 \text{ mol}^{-1/2}$)		B ($\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)		Λ_m^0 ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)		$\eta_0\Lambda_m^0$ ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cP}$)	
	CuSO ₄	ZnSO ₄	CuSO ₄	ZnSO ₄	CuSO ₄	ZnSO ₄	CuSO ₄	ZnSO ₄	CuSO ₄	ZnSO ₄	CuSO ₄	ZnSO ₄	CuSO ₄	ZnSO ₄
0.02 mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride														
298.15	76.68	121.84	0.40541	0.10656	0.1157	-4.1929	0.0373	0.0171	0.253	0.2769	209.14	217.11	190.20	196.89
303.15	77.33	122.45	0.39974	0.10544	0.1459	-4.1849	0.0447	0.0218	0.246	0.2703	239.58	257.65	195.16	209.89
308.15	78.46	123.21	0.38801	0.10272	0.1760	-4.1769	0.0542	0.0265	0.240	0.2626	268.25	300.25	196.86	221.02
313.15	79.41	123.90	0.38125	0.09898	0.2062	-4.1689	0.0639	0.0330	0.231	0.2558	302.46	349.66	200.95	231.59
0.04 mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride														
298.15	81.53	121.94	0.32965	0.22388	0.2529	0.2284	0.0130	0.0158	0.288	0.2727	228.22	260.78	212.55	242.88
303.15	82.88	123.23	0.32831	0.22035	0.2887	0.2874	0.0193	0.0204	0.281	0.2645	259.23	311.43	216.45	260.03
308.15	85.23	124.42	0.31143	0.20947	0.3246	0.3464	0.0270	0.0252	0.272	0.2560	297.60	369.63	224.02	278.24
313.15	86.94	126.03	0.30165	0.18745	0.3604	0.4054	0.0379	0.0307	0.265	0.2483	334.32	425.95	225.10	286.87
0.06 mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride														
298.15	90.85	123.94	0.91630	9.0020	0.4242	0.0482	0.006	0.0238	0.246	0.2702	249.22	275.62	240.77	265.57
303.15	93.09	124.46	0.31087	8.9494	0.4747	0.1612	0.016	0.0281	0.238	0.2627	285.02	322.27	244.48	279.53
308.15	95.10	125.67	0.28890	8.8500	0.5252	0.2737	0.026	0.0329	0.231	0.2580	319.87	376.10	247.55	292.77
313.15	97.85	127.32	0.23810	8.5335	0.5757	0.3872	0.039	0.0374	0.224	0.2510	360.04	434.62	249.50	302.09

^d m is the molality of CuSO₄ or ZnSO₄ in 0.01 mol kg⁻¹ (maltose + water + NaCl) solvent. Standard uncertainties U are $U(T) = 0.05 \text{ K}$, $U(p) = 0.000032 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$.

Fig. 5. Limiting apparent molar expansibility ϕ_E^0 as a function of temperature T for copper sulphate in different mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 mol kg^{-1} aqueous sodium chloride.

Fig. 6. Limiting apparent molar expansibility ϕ_E^0 as a function of temperature T for zinc sulphate in different mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 mol kg^{-1} aqueous sodium chloride.

high polarity the water molecules closest to the dissolved ion are strongly attached to it, forming what is known as primary solvent sheath or inner hydration shell. The positively charged ions attract the negative ends of water molecule. The ordered structure within the primary shell creates though hydrogen bonding a region in which the surrounding waters are also somewhat ordered, this is the outer hydration shell. The ions orient solvent molecules in one or more shells around themselves, forming a region (primary hydration shell) of increased structure and a region of reduced structure (partially ordered region) and an unperturbed region (bulk water). For smaller

ion region primary hydration shell dominates hence they act as structure makers while for larger ions partially ordered region dominates and they act as net structure breakers.

The structure making/breaking capacity of zinc sulphate and copper sulphate hydrates was interpreted with the help of Hepler's reasoning^{19,20} using sign of $[\partial^2\phi_v^0/\partial T^2]_p$.

The structure-making solutes have positive values of $[\partial^2\phi_v^0/\partial T^2]_p$, whereas structure-breaking solutes should show negative values of $[\partial^2\phi_v^0/\partial T^2]_p$. In the present case, it has been observed that $[\partial^2\phi_v^0/\partial T^2]_p$ is positive for zinc sulphate (or copper sulphate) in all the studied solvents indicating that hydrates of zinc sulphate and copper sulphate behave as structure-makers in 0.02, 0.04 and 0.06 mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 mol kg^{-1} aqueous NaCl solutions.

Viscosity studies :

The viscosity data (Table 2) has been analysed on the basis of Jones-Dole equation²¹,

$$\eta_{\text{rel}} = \frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = 1 + Am^{1/2} + Bm \quad (6)$$

where η is the viscosity of electrolyte solution, η_0 is the viscosity of the pure solvent, m is the molal concentration of electrolyte, A and B are the two coefficients of Jones-Dole equation. The values of A and B have been determined from the intercept and slope of linear plots of $[\eta/\eta_0 - 1]/m^{1/2}$ versus $m^{1/2}$ (Figs. 7 and 8). The values of A and B calculated for different solutions are recorded in Table 3.

Parameter A of Jones-Dole equation represents the contribution from solute-solute or ion-ion interactions²². The values of A , shows that ion-ion interactions increase with increase in temperature, which may be due to the presence of opposite charged ions. The B parameter is the measures of structure-making/breaking behaviour of the electrolyte and also an indicator for solute-solvent interactions in the system²³. The temperature variation of B (dB/dT) is more significant criteria for solute-solvent interactions (Figs. 9 and 10). A positive B -coefficient for aqueous maltose can be interpreted as merely due to bulky size ion²⁴.

Fig. 7. Jones-Dole plot for copper sulphate in different mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 mol kg⁻¹ aqueous sodium chloride.

Fig. 9. Variation of Jones-Dole coefficient B with temperature T for copper sulphate in different mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 mol kg⁻¹ aqueous sodium chloride.

Fig. 8. Jones-Dole plot for zinc sulphate in different mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 mol kg⁻¹ aqueous sodium chloride.

Fig. 10. Variation of Jones-Dole coefficient B with temperature T for zinc sulphate in different mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 mol kg⁻¹ aqueous sodium chloride.

The sign of dB/dT determine the structure-maker/breaker behaviour of electrolyte as negative dB/dT is shown by structure-maker electrolytes and structure-breaker will have positive dB/dT . In the present study, the negative temperature coefficient of B (dB/dT) has been obtained for zinc sulphate (or copper sulphate) in all the studied solvents (Figs. 9 and 10) thereby indicating structure-makers/promoters nature of these electrolytes in 0.02, 0.04 and 0.06 mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 mol kg⁻¹ aqueous NaCl solutions.

Conductance studies :

The concentration dependence of molar conductance

for zinc sulphate (or copper sulphate) has been analysed with Onsager's equation.

$$\Lambda_m = \Lambda_m^0 - K\sqrt{m} \quad (7)$$

The limiting molar conductance Λ_m^0 has been obtained from the intercept of Onsager's plot (Figs. 11 and 12). Λ_m^0 was found to be increasing with temperature for zinc sulphate (or copper sulphate) in all the studied solvents showing an apprehensive increase in solute-solvent interactions with rise in temperature. It may be attributed to the increased dissociation of solute molecules and to the free mobility of ions at infinite dilution with rise in tem-

Fig. 11. Onsager plot for copper sulphate in 0.02 mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 mol kg⁻¹ aqueous NaCl.

Fig. 12. Onsager plot for zinc sulphate in 0.02 mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 mol kg⁻¹ aqueous NaCl.

perature. Therefore evaluation of Λ_m^0 should give equally reliable information regarding ion-solvent interactions^{25,26}.

Walden product has also been obtained for both the sulphates in all the studied solvent systems and its variation with temperature has been utilised for the determination of structure-maker/breaker nature of studied sulphates. The temperature coefficient of Walden product i.e. $[\partial(\Lambda_m^0 \eta_0) / \partial T]$ was found to be positive for zinc sulphate (or copper sulphate) in 0.02, 0.04 and 0.06 mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 mol kg⁻¹ aqueous NaCl solutions, suggests that ZnSO₄·7H₂O and CuSO₄·5H₂O act as structure-makers in the studied solvents.

Fig. 13. Variation of Walden product for copper sulphate in various mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 mol kg⁻¹ aqueous NaCl.

Fig. 14. Variation of Walden product for zinc sulphate in various mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 mol kg⁻¹ aqueous NaCl.

In the measurement of conductance of solutions the conductance of zinc sulphate and copper sulphate was measured in water and then in aqueous 0.01 m sodium chloride solutions. The measured values of molar conductance and limiting molar conductance of these solutions are reported in Table 5 and Table 6. The measured values of these solutions were not subtracted and were used as such. When ionic compounds are prepared in water solution and then isolated as solids, the crystals often have molecules of water trapped in the structure. Compounds where molecules of water are associated with the ions of the compound are called hydrates or hydrated salts. Since these compounds are ionic, they are also called hydrated salts. So the solutions of the hydrated salts were made by using weight method where; total mass of hy-

Table 5. Molar conductance of CuSO₄ and ZnSO₄ in water and 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride

Concentration (mol kg ⁻¹)	Molar conductance Λ_m ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)		Molar conductance Λ_m ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	
	Water		Water + 0.01 m NaCl	
	CuSO ₄	ZnSO ₄	CuSO ₄	ZnSO ₄
<i>T</i> (K) = 298.15				
0.01	131.25	133.73	208.01	201.03
0.02	123.25	125.84	186.08	184.17
0.04	110.96	113.52	159.96	159.41
0.06	102.21	104.18	132.11	141.94
0.08	94.51	95.81	111.92	124.23
0.10	86.54	88.2	93.36	111.64
0.12	81.11	82.35	79.14	99.39
<i>T</i> (K) = 303.15				
0.01	144.65	146.04	230.51	217.47
0.02	132.25	136.13	203.53	198.59
0.04	118.32	121.29	169.87	173.07
0.06	109.36	111.40	142.99	154.01
0.08	101.21	102.77	122.16	135.37
0.10	94.56	96.65	101.08	121.82
0.12	82.96	87.52	86.61	109.19
<i>T</i> (K) = 308.15				
0.01	155.69	159.42	250.11	237.05
0.02	145.39	149.51	221.59	216.14
0.04	131.25	134.17	184.87	187.33
0.06	121.35	124.01	156.79	167.01
0.08	112.58	114.47	131.80	150.14
0.10	106.87	107.10	107.39	133.40
0.12	98.96	100.54	91.81	118.20
<i>T</i> (K) = 313.15				
0.01	169.32	171.88	266.79	253.71
0.02	158.36	161.96	237.23	232.78
0.04	143.85	145.35	197.93	202.69
0.06	128.25	132.57	165.42	180.08
0.08	121.25	124.90	137.69	160.03
0.10	114.36	115.49	113.34	142.68
0.12	107.85	108.43	98.23	128.28

Table 6. Limiting molar conductance of CuSO₄ and ZnSO₄ in water and 0.01 m aqueous sodium chloride

Temperature <i>T</i> (K)	Limiting molar conductance		Limiting molar conductance	
	Λ_m^0 ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)		Λ_m^0 ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	
	Water		0.01 m NaCl	
	CuSO ₄	ZnSO ₄	CuSO ₄	ZnSO ₄
298.15	131.88	155.55	261.45	243.07
303.15	143.71	169.19	287.89	261.80
308.15	155.07	183.41	314.60	284.64
313.15	168.57	198.13	336.59	305.64

drated salt = mass of the anhydrous salt + mass of waters of hydration.

Conclusion

The positive sign of $[\partial^2\phi_v^0/\partial T^2]_p$ and negative sign of dB/dT for ZnSO₄.7H₂O and CuSO₄.5H₂O shows that these hydrated sulphates behave as structure-makers in 0.02, 0.04 and 0.06 mass fraction of maltose in 0.01 mol kg⁻¹ aqueous NaCl solutions. The positive temperature coefficient of Walden product support these results.

References

1. Jean-Pierre Morel, C. Lhermet and Nicole Morel-Derrosiers, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1988, **84**, 2567.
2. V. Vitagilano, G. Borriello, C. Della Volpe and O. Ortona, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1986, **15**, 811.
3. V. K. Syal, S. Chauhan and Pawan K. Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 860.
4. S. Kant and S. Kumar, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 2013, **58**, 1294.
5. S. Kant, A. Kumar and S. Kumar, *J. Mol. Liq.*, 2009, **150**, 39.
6. A. Sinha and M. N. Roy, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 2006, **51**, 1415.
7. Xin-Xeu Li, G. Zhao, Dong-Sheng Liu and Wen-Wei Cao, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 2009, **54**, 890.
8. J. L. Neal and D. A. I. Goring, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1970, **74**, 658.
9. R. Saeed, S. Massod, M. Ashfaq and A. Irfan, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 2009, **54**, 3125.
10. M. L. Parmar, P. Sharma and M. K. Guleria, *Indian J. Chem.*, 2009, **48A**, 57.
11. R. R. Gupta and M. Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2008, **85**, 176.
12. K. Zhuo, Y. Chen, W. Wang and J. Wang, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 2008, **53**, 2022.
13. R. L. Blokhra and M. L. Parmar, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1974, **27**, 1407.
14. J. K. Dash, M. Sahu, M. Chakraborty and V. Chakravorty, *J. Mol. Liq.*, 2000, **84**, 215.
15. S. Baluja, A. Solanki and N. Kachhadia, *Russ. J. Phys. Chem.*, 2007, **81**, 742.
16. F. J. Millero and J. H. Knox, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1973, **18**, 407.
17. M. N. Roy, R. Dey and A. Jha, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 2001, **46**, 1327.
18. F. J. Millero, "The partial molal volumes of electrolytes in aqueous solutions" in : 'Water and aqueous solutions : Structure Thermodynamics and Transport Processes in Water and Aqueous Solutions', ed. R. A. Horne, Wiley Interscience, New York, USA, 1972, **2219**, 519.
19. F. J. Millero and Hansen W. Drost, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, **72**, 1758.
20. L. G. Hepler, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1969, **47**, 4613.
21. Robert S. Dordickt and W. Drost-Hansen, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1981, **85**, 1086.
22. J. D. Pandey and Y. Akhtar, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1997, **109**, 289.
23. M. N. Roy, V. K. Dakua and B. Sinha, *Int. J. Thermophys.*, 2007, **28**, 1275.
24. T. S. Sharma and J. C. Ahluwalia, *Rev. Chem. Soc. London II*, 1973, **203**.
25. W. R. Gilkerson and M. D. Jackson, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **101**, 4096.
26. John O'M. Bockris and Amulya K. N. Reddy, "Modern Electrochemistry", 2nd ed., Plenum Press, New York, 1998.